

Contributions to in-service primary teachers practice from their engagement in mathematics landscapes of investigation

Contribuições para a formação contínua de professores do primeiro ciclo a partir de seu engajamento em cenários para investigação

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Abstract

In Mathematics Education research, studies have pointed out the existence of little attention in initial primary teacher education for the exploration of mathematical content from critical discussions aimed at its pedagogical use in understanding emerging social problems, such as social inequalities, climate and environmental changes, and violence (Gutstein, 2018). However, the treatment of these and other issues in mathematics classes has increasingly become a requirement of basic school curricula. As a consequence, many primary teachers, especially those at the beginning of their careers, do not feel prepared to work with these matters in mathematics classes, which leads them to seek subsequent education. Although this situation is known and remarked upon in the Mathematics Education literature, there are few studies specifically aimed at understanding how teachers learn and implement investigation tasks that allow for the treatment of social issues in their mathematics classes as a result of their engagement in in-service teacher education. In this way, using the perspective of Critical Mathematics Education, the objective of this research is to understand how primary school teachers working with landscapes of investigation develop from the study and elaboration of teaching tasks. Critical Mathematics Education is mostly concerned with the connection between mathematics education and issues such as equity, social justice, classroom dialogue, project development, and inclusion (Skovsmose, 2023). The development of landscapes of investigation has been a way to address these concerns in classroom. They have also been shown to be a way to address the development of meaningful activities in the classroom that favour the construction of mathematical concepts and ideas. For Skovsmose (2023), landscapes of investigation can be defined as learning environments that provide students with opportunities to build their own conclusions, accepting the invitation to analyse didactic

situations and problems with the principles of the investigation, exploration, questioning, and surveying of hypotheses and ideas. Furthermore, they provide opportunities for dialogue, cooperation, research, and decision making. In addition, works such as that by Ponte, Brocardo, and Oliveira (2015) have provided guidelines for teachers to conduct investigative classes in the field of mathematics education, and to build and adapt teaching activities, seeking to favour the learning of their students. To achieve the objectives of this study, we use a case study methodology with a qualitative approach. We will analyse teacher engagement in a teacher education program aimed at Portuguese primary in-service teachers. In this program, developed in 75 hours with four stages, we will explore teachers' development of tasks based on the landscape of investigation in mathematics classes. The first stage encompasses the theoretical study of critical mathematics education ideas related to landscapes of investigation. Teachers are stimulated to engage in tasks with this perspective related to mathematical concepts, semi-reality, and reality (Skovsmose, 2023). The second stage involves the collaborative planning of one or more lessons based on landscapes of investigation-based by primary teachers. During this stage, teachers "test" the proposals they have developed with their peers and often strive to anticipate unforeseen situations that may arise due to unpredictability. The classroom tasks are implemented in the third stage, with the support of teacher-trainer. It is crucial to observe student learning, reflect on the approach taken in the classroom, identify challenges and opportunities, among other considerations. Finally, in the fourth stage, there is collective reflection on the practice carried out within the training context. At this point, everyone shares their experiences, reports the dynamics applied in the classroom, highlights key outcomes, and assesses areas for improvement, change, or continuation. Participants also discuss their difficulties and what proved significant in the lesson, receiving feedback and suggestions, among other aspects. Once the four stages are completed, a new cycle can be initiated, considering previous experiences. Our study is in the data collection phase and carrying out teacher education program. There are 12 primary school teachers in this education program. We carry out a complete cycle during the second academic semester of 2023/2024. We will do a second cycle in the first academic semester of 2024/2025. The dynamic of the teacher education program could be reapplied in other contexts, favouring more in-service teachers can be benefited, improving mathematical learning of their students. Every country needs that more children can be engaged at science, and mathematics. In this way, improving their mathematics learning is critical. The results of this study will illuminate the development of continuing education practices aimed at improving mathematics education in the primary years of schooling. The audience for our study is made up of university professors; researchers in the

field of mathematics education interested in understanding practices related to in-service primary teacher education; primary school teacher trainers interested in understanding the potential of creating landscapes of investigation for the teaching of mathematics; teachers (in-service and pre-service) of primary education interested in new pedagogical practices aimed at working with landscapes of investigation in their classes; developers of institutional policies for the continuing education of primary school teachers interested in the discussion of teaching strategies for mathematics in primary education; and ministries of primary education interested in training state primary school teachers.

Keywords: teacher education; critical mathematics education; mathematics education.

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